

LCA of CFRP in Aerospace: Energy Modelling of Autoclave Curing

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ICCM 23, Belfast, July - August 2023

Outline

- Motivation and objectives
- Autoclave curing
- Energy monitoring using power meter
- Parametric models for energy consumption
- Results and discussion
- Conclusion

CFRP in Aerospace Applications - Advantages

High Stiffness (Rigidity) High specific strength High Corrosion and Fatigue Resistance

Production of Lightweight Structures

Increased Fuel Efficiency

25% in Boeing 787 (ICCT 2017)

Lower Operating Cost

Up to 3.5% (NASA)

Reduced Emissions

Up to 20% of aviation CO₂ target

Materials used in Airbus A350 XWB (Airbus Operations)

CFRP Value Chain in Aerospace Applications

Resource Depletion from fossil fuel

PAN based fibres
▪ made from petroleum,

Material extraction and processing

Component Manufacture

Energy intensive manufacturing

Joining

Operation

Benefits focus mainly on operational phase

Recycling

Disposal

Challenges with recycling thermoset

End of Life

Manufacturing CFRP in Aerospace Applications

- Mainstream is thermoset CFRP with autoclave curing

Manual Collation

Automated Collation
– AFP Robots

- What are the energy Intensive process Steps?
- What parameters influence them? 🤔

Goal and Objectives

- Create reliable energy inventory data for autoclave CFRP manufacturing
 - Can be used in LCA studies and cost estimations
- Identify hot spots regarding energy consumption
- Identify process and design parameters that influence energy consumption
 - For optimisation

How?

- Energy monitoring using power meter – Experimental study
- Energy estimation using thermodynamics based models

Energy Monitoring: CFRP Panel Manufacture

- ✓ Manufacture a CF/Epoxy panel via manual collation and autoclave curing.
 - Monitor Energy Consumption
 - Using 3-phase Power meter
 - Convert power logs to energy logs - integral
- ✓ Identify process steps with the most energy consumption

Results: Energy Monitoring

Autoclave contributes 91%

Results: Autoclave Energy Monitoring

- Power Log
- Energy Log
17.6kWh
- First 35 mins
stood out
- Temperature
and Pressure
Cycle

Thermodynamics Based Models

Two different models were used

- MRT LBM –
Multirelaxation Time
Lattice Boltzman
Method
- Analytical Method

Why?

- Parametric and Scalable
- Breakdown energy
consumption - Heat
absorbing elements and
heat losses

Thermodynamics Based Models: MRT LBM Method

2D Multi-Relaxation Time (MRT) lattice Boltzmann method

$$f_i(x + \vec{e}_i \partial t, t + \partial t) = f_i(x, t) - \frac{1}{\tau} (f_i(x, t) - f_i^{eq}(x, t))$$

+

Energy Equation - Navier-Stokes Method

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{k}{\rho C_p} \nabla^2 T - \vec{u} \cdot \nabla T$$

Diffusion term: Nonlinear advection term

+

Fourier Heat Equation in 2D with convective boundary conditions

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = \frac{k}{\rho C_p} \left(\frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 T}{\partial y^2} \right)$$

Simulated Autoclave Energy Consumption

Thermodynamics Based Models: Energy Conservation

Ist Order Thermodynamics Law: Energy Conservation

$$Q_{inflow} = \frac{Q_{heat} + Q_{loss}}{\eta_{eff}} \times \eta_{Loading}$$

$$Q_{heat} = \rho \cdot V \cdot C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t}$$

$$Q_{heat} = (M_F C_{p_F} + M_R C_{p_R} + M_{con} C_{p_{con}} + M_{air} C_{p_{air}} + M_{autoclave} C_{p_{autoclave}}) \cdot (T_{cure} - T_{\infty})$$

$$Q_{loss} = A \times \frac{K_a}{s} \times (T_r - T_{out}) \times t$$

Considering heating energy for heating up only laminates,

$$Q_{heat_L} = \rho \cdot V \cdot C_p \frac{\partial T}{\partial t} = h \cdot A (T - T_{\infty})$$

Results: Model Comparison

- ✓ 10% difference between the two methods
- ✓ MRT LBM was a better match to the monitored result (only 1% difference.)
- ✓ Analytical Method has the least computational effort

Simulated Autoclave Energy Consumption

Results: Energy Breakdown

Energy consumed by each heat absorbing element within the autoclave.

- ✓ Heat absorbed by the composite part < 3%
- ✓ Heat transfer to autoclave body contributed 75%
- ✓ Heat loss through the walls 22%

Results: What-if Analysis

Influence of Design and Process Parameters

- Loading autoclave to its maximum capacity is more energy efficient

Results: What-if Analysis

Influence of Design and Process Parameters

- ✓ Cure temperature influence energy consumption
- ✓ Cycle time also influence energy consumption
- ✓ Thermal mass dominate for short cycles
- ✓ Thermal mass and heat losses dominate for short cycles

Conclusion

- ✓ Autoclave curing is a major contributor to energy consumption of CFRP Manufacturing
 - Energy Efficiency of Autoclave curing lies below 3%
- ✓ Thermodynamics based models can be used to create energy estimates of autoclave curing
 - Code readily available under MIT license (Please scan QR code)
 - Model can be used in autoclave design optimisation, process optimisation, energy inventory especially in aerospace industry where data is proprietary and isn't readily available.
- ✓ Autoclave thermal mass and heat losses are major contributors to energy consumption of autoclave curing.

GitHub

Models for Estimating Energy Consumption

Composites: Part A 166 (2023) 107365

ELSEVIER

Contents lists available at [ScienceDirect](#)

Composites Part A

journal homepage: www.elsevier.com/locate/compositesa

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Thank You